

ISic0100

I.Sicily inscription 0100

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Found 1768 in vicinity of Castle

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 120

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Antiae M(arci) f(iliae) Cleo
2. patrae sacerdoti
3. ex voluntate pop(uli)
4. d(ecreto) d(ecurionum) inpensa pub(lico)
5. remissa cuius d[e]
6. dicatione ple[beis]
7. singuli decu[ri]
8. onum filis b[ini]
9. decurioni[bus]
10. quini den[arii]
11. dati sunt

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

To Antia Cleopatra, daughter of Marcus, priestess, by the will of the people,

(erected) by decree of the city council, with the expense reimbursed from public funds. On the occasion of whose dedication (?) one denarius was given to (each of) the plebs, two to the sons of decuriones, and five to the decuriones.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285328

EDR 127535

EDCS 22100053

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7352 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650796>)

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Manganaro, G. 1988. *La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. ANRW.* 2.11.1: 3-89. At tav.16

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